

Sample ID **3-1 (Combined)**

Operator ID **user**

Notes

Elapsed Time	00:01:00
Median Diam.	99.5 nm
Mean Diam.	99.7 nm
Polydispersity	0.005
GSD	1.073

Lognormal Size Distribution

d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)	d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)	d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)
88.5	26	5	97.7	97	40	104.3	80	75
90.8	44	10	98.6	99	45	105.6	70	80
92.4	58	15	99.5	100	50	107.0	58	85
93.7	70	20	100.3	99	55	108.9	44	90
94.8	80	25	101.3	97	60	111.7	26	95
95.8	87	30	102.2	93	65			
96.8	93	35	103.2	87	70			